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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 27

Issue 2

Pages: 258-273

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2557

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14007254

Manuscript Accepted: 10-10-2024

Generation Alpha Students' Behavior as Digital Natives and their Learning Engagement

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Abstract

Characterized by early Internet exposure, Gen A's learning preferences and behavioral patterns are different from previous generations. The study aimed to investigate the impact of learning styles and teaching styles on the learning engagement of Generation Alpha students. It sought to (1) determine their learning styles, (2) assess their teachers' teaching styles, (3) examine their learning engagement, (4) whether there is a significant difference in the learning engagement when grouped according to learning styles, and (5) examine if there is a significant difference in the learning engagement when grouped according teaching styles. Using a descriptive-comparative research design, the data was obtained from 100 Gen A students. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and ANOVA. Results revealed that Gen A students utilize the visual learning style the most, are more Behaviorally Engaged, and perceive the Facilitator or Activity Style as the most used by teachers. ANOVA results conclude that there is a statistically significant difference in student engagement among different learning style groups. Visual learners exhibit significantly higher engagement than others. Teaching styles also have a significant influence on student engagement with the Facilitator and Delegator styles resulting in higher engagement. The study concluded that both learning styles and teaching styles have significant influence on students' engagement. Additionally, teacher training programs should prioritize addressing diverse learning styles to optimize engagement and learning. Thus, recognizing the influence of teaching styles on student engagement can lead to more dynamic and inclusive learning environments for a new generation of learners.

Keywords: *generation alpha students, behavior, digital natives, learning engagement*

Introduction

Generation Alpha or Gen A refers to individuals born in the early 2010s who will continue to grow up through 2025 (Kizer, 2024). Characterized by their early exposure to digital technologies and the Internet, Gen A's learning preferences, social interactions, and behavioral patterns are distinctly different from previous generations (McCrinkle & Wolfinger, 2020). Academic institutions are already aware of the need to improve how technology is incorporated into the classroom. The learning preferences of this generation are multimodal, including auditory, visual, and kinesthetic elements (Mayer 2009, Hattie 2008). This generational shift poses new challenges and opportunities for educators, particularly in secondary education, where foundational academic and social development occurs.

The term "digital natives" has gained prominence in describing Generation Alpha, emphasizing their early exposure to and integration of technology into their daily lives. Prensky (2001) first introduced the concept of digital natives to describe individuals who have grown up in the digital age, contrasting them with digital immigrants who adopt technology later in life. For Generation Alpha, technology is not just a tool but an integral part of their environment, shaping their cognitive processes and social interactions (Palfrey & Gasser, 2016).

Technology has revolutionized the way Generation Alpha learns, offering access to a vast array of information and educational resources. The traditional classroom is evolving into a digital learning environment, where interactive tools and multimedia content enhance engagement and knowledge retention (Hsin & Cigas, 2013). Accessibility, simplicity of use, convenience, and interaction are common elements that are increasingly defining quality education. Technology plays a function in the field of education (Raja & Nagasubramani, 2018). However, the prevalence of digital media also raises concerns about attention spans, information overload, and the need for critical digital literacy skills (Bennett & Maton, 2010). Educators and policymakers must adapt to these changes to ensure that Generation Alpha receives a well-rounded education that prepares them for the challenges of the digital age.

Research has consistently shown that teachers' perceptions of their students can significantly influence classroom dynamics, teaching strategies, and, ultimately, students' academic performance (Hattie, 2008; Rosenthal & Jacobson, 1968). Moreover, a harmonious environment created by a teacher can enhance learning. Therefore, schools that are successful for multilingual learners can have strong teacher-student relationships (C, E., and Jr., G., 2020). As a result, understanding secondary education teachers' perspectives of Gen A students' behavior as digital natives is very important.

The relationship between learning styles and learners' engagement has been a topic of considerable interest in educational research. Studies such as those conducted by Brown et al. (2009) have consistently shown that students' learning styles play a crucial role in shaping their level of engagement in the learning process. When instructional methods align with students' preferred learning styles, they are more likely to demonstrate heightened levels of engagement, as evidenced by Johnson et al. (2020). This finding underscores

the importance of recognizing and accommodating diverse learning styles to promote active participation and meaningful learning experiences.

Moreover, research by Smith (2018) emphasizes the significant impact of providing learning experiences that align with students' preferred learning styles on their engagement and academic performance. When students are presented with content and activities that resonate with their individual learning preferences, they are more likely to feel motivated and invested in the learning process, resulting in improved outcomes. This highlights the need for educators to adopt flexible instructional approaches that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of learners, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. By leveraging insights from research on learning styles, educators can tailor their teaching methods to enhance learners' engagement, ultimately contributing to more positive learning outcomes.

In addition to understanding the impact of learning styles on learners' engagement, it is crucial to consider the role of teaching styles in shaping the educational experience. Research suggests that the instructional methods employed by educators can significantly influence students' levels of engagement and academic performance (Davis & Smith, 2019). For instance, authoritarian teaching styles characterized by strict control and limited student autonomy may hinder students' willingness to actively participate in the learning process (Rubie-Davies, 2015). In contrast, more student-centered approaches, such as facilitator or activity styles, promote collaboration, critical thinking, and intrinsic motivation, leading to higher levels of engagement (Brookfield, 2015). By exploring the relationship between teaching styles and learners' engagement, educators can identify effective strategies for creating inclusive and dynamic learning environments that cater to the diverse needs and preferences of Generation Alpha students.

Theoretical Framework of the Study. The study is anchored on the Cognitive Load Theory (CLT), which posits that learners have limited cognitive resources for processing information, and instructional materials should be designed to manage these cognitive loads effectively (Sweller, 1988). In the context of the research topic on learning styles and teaching styles, CLT suggests that matching instructional methods to students' preferred learning styles can help reduce cognitive load and enhance engagement. For instance, visual learners may benefit from diagrams and charts to process information, while auditory learners may prefer lectures or audio recordings. By aligning teaching strategies with students' cognitive preferences, educators can optimize learning experiences and improve engagement.

Research Questions

This study aims to identify the influence of learning styles and teaching styles on the learning engagement of Gen A students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Gen A students in terms of their:
 - 1.1. learning styles;
 - 1.2. their assessment of their teachers' teaching styles; and
 - 1.3. level of engagement?
2. Is there a significant difference between Gen A students' learning engagement and learning styles?
3. Do the Gen A students' learning engagement vary when grouped according to teaching styles?

Literature Review

Generation Alpha

Generation Alpha, born into a digital era, exhibits distinct behavioral patterns influenced by their exposure to technology from an early age. This literature review examines how Gen A's behavior is characterized by increased digital literacy, a preference for visual and interactive learning, and reliance on digital platforms for social learning.

Generational theory posits that individuals born within a specific period share certain socio-cultural experiences, shaping their attitudes, behaviors, and expectations (Strauss & Howe, 1991). This theoretical framework has been applied to understand the impact of generational cohorts on educational practices and learning outcomes. Studies have focused on identifying the distinctive characteristics of each generation and adjusting educational strategies to better meet their needs (Williams & Page, 2011).

Generation A is distinguished by its ubiquity with digital technology from a young age, leading to unique learning preferences and behavioral patterns (McCrindle, 2014). This generation is expected to exhibit greater familiarity with multimedia tools, a preference for interactive and digital learning environments, and potentially shorter attention spans due to constant digital stimulation (Rosen, 2010; Holloway et al., 2019).

The concept of digital natives, introduced by Prensky (2001), describes individuals born into an inherently digital world, thus speaking the 'language' of technology fluently from an early age. Generation Alpha amplifies this concept as they are introduced to technology almost from birth, navigating tablets and smartphones with ease (Prensky, 2001). This generation is witnessing unprecedented exposure to digital technology from an early age, which influences their learning preferences and styles. Research on the learning styles of Gen A is still developing, but we can draw on existing theories and early studies to understand their tendencies towards visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning.

Visual Learners. Visual learners prefer to learn through seeing. They find it easier to understand information through images, diagrams, and visual presentations. For Generation Alpha, the integration of multimedia in learning environments is critical. Richard Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning suggests that individuals learn better when words and pictures are used together rather than words alone. This theory is particularly relevant for visual learners in Gen A, as they are growing up with interactive and visual technologies like tablets and smartboards which can support this style of learning.

Auditory Learners. Auditory learners absorb information best through listening. They benefit from lectures, discussions, and audio materials. With the rise of podcasts, audiobooks, and other digital audio content, auditory learners have more resources than ever. The theory of Auditory Learning, derived from the VAK (Visual, Auditory, Kinesthetic) learning styles model, emphasizes the importance of hearing and verbalizing information as key components of learning. For Gen A, whose lifestyle often includes multi-tasking with digital devices, auditory learning can be integrated into daily activities more seamlessly.

Kinesthetic learners. Kinesthetic learners are hands-on and learn through doing and touching. For children in Generation Alpha, learning through physical interaction is essential, even in a digital age. The experiential learning theory by David Kolb emphasizes the role of experience in the learning process. Gen A learners can benefit significantly from interactive technology that involves touch and physical interaction, such as virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR), which provide immersive learning experiences that align well with kinesthetic learning preferences.

For Generation Alpha, traditional categorizations into visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning styles must be reconsidered and expanded upon in light of digital advancements. Modern educational technologies offer new ways to cater to these learning styles, making learning more effective and engaging for this generation. As research continues to evolve, it will be crucial to assess how these technologies can be integrated into educational practices to best serve the needs of Gen A learners.

Teaching Styles

Teaching styles are crucial in shaping students' learning experiences. Educators employ various approaches to instruction, each with unique methods and outcomes. In this study the researchers focus on five key teaching styles: Authority, Delegator, Demonstrator, Facilitator, and Hybrid.

Authority or Lecture Style. This style is characterized by the teacher being the primary source of information, delivering lectures to students who are expected to listen and take notes. This traditional approach has been criticized for its passive nature, where students may not be actively engaged in the learning process (McKeachie, 2002).

Delegator or Group Style. Teacher acts as a facilitator, delegating tasks and responsibilities to student groups. Students are encouraged to collaborate, discuss ideas, and solve problems together. This style promotes active learning and fosters teamwork skills (Brookfield, 2015).

Demonstrator or Coach Style. The demonstrator or coach style involves the teacher demonstrating concepts or skills while providing guidance and feedback to students. This hands-on approach allows students to observe and learn from the teacher's example, promoting experiential learning (Gardner, 2006).

Facilitator or Activity Style. Teachers adopting this style focus on creating interactive learning experiences through various activities such as group discussions, role-plays, and simulations. The facilitator guides students through these activities, encouraging critical thinking and problem-solving (Nilson, 2016).

Learning Engagement

Moreover, the engagement of Generation Alpha in learning environments is highly influenced by the integration of technology. Studies suggest that the use of interactive and multimedia instructional strategies can enhance engagement and learning outcomes for this generation. However, the challenge remains to balance technological use with the development of social and emotional skills (Rideout, 2016).

Educational strategies for Generation Alpha must consider their digital nativity, suggesting a shift towards more personalized, technology-integrated, and collaborative learning environments. The implementation of blended learning models and the use of gamification can potentially increase engagement and cater to their learning preferences effectively (Clark & Mayer, 2016).

DepEd Order No. 42, S. 2016 orders to give educators the chance to consider how best to support students' learning as well as what has to be taught in order for them to learn it. Along with recognizing the diversity of learners in the classroom and being devoted to their success, these guidelines also aim to empower teachers to deliver high-quality instruction that makes use of a variety of instructional and formative assessment strategies, including the use of information and communications technologies (ICTs). Additionally, these guidelines allow teachers to mentor, support, and guide learners as they develop and assess their learning across the curriculum.

Behavioral Engagement. McCabe and Wallace (2018) claim that Generation Alpha's upbringing in the digital sphere has resulted in special cognitive and behavioral needs. Being naive to digital, they need venues for education and learning that are interactive,

captivating, and cooperative. They like learning materials offered in a multi-media format and are used to swiftly and easily obtaining information. This suggests that traditional teaching strategies like lectures and textbooks might not be as successful with this generation.

Since Generation Alpha places a high importance on uniqueness and self-expression, their learning settings must include chances for creative expression and exploration. When given the opportunity to voice their thoughts and opinions in original ways, they are more inclined to interact with the educational materials. Project-based learning, interactive technology, and imaginative assignments that push students to think beyond the box are a few examples of this. According to a PwC survey, 86% of Generation Alpha parents think that their kids have a strong feeling of uniqueness and are more inclined than earlier generations to forge their own course in life (PwC, 2017).

Agentic Engagement. Agentic engagement involves the actions and words of students aimed at fostering a more supportive learning environment for themselves (Reeve & Jang, 2022). This form of engagement is proactive, as students actively participate in shaping their educational experience rather than passively absorbing information. Through agentic engagement, students might ask questions, seek feedback, suggest activities, or express their preferences and needs. By doing so, they not only enhance their own learning but also contribute to creating a classroom atmosphere that is more responsive and attuned to the diverse needs of all students. This dynamic interaction helps build a more interactive and personalized educational setting, ultimately promoting better learning outcomes and greater student satisfaction. Students improve the quality of the learning environment around them by using their agency and initiative (Reeve, 2020).

Cognitive Engagement. Cognitive engagement is the least reliable and mysterious construct component, (Wang & Fredricks, 2014) understood as the extent to which students devote themselves to the learning process and tactics. While some academics associate this component with the capacity for self-regulation in learning procedures (Walker, Greene, & Mansell, 2006; Clery & Zimmerman, 2012).

Amazon's Alexa and Apple's Siri have gained more significance for Generation Alpha than their parents or friends. Rather than engaging in outdoor or real-life activities, they prefer staying in their comfort zones and playing mobile games such as Pokémon, Xbox, and PUBG. The prevalence of online gaming has become so widespread that it is now recognized as an issue by the American Psychiatric Association and the World Health Organization, which have termed it Internet Gaming Disorder and Gaming Disorder, respectively, in the DSM-5 and ICD-11 (WHO, 2016). Arora and Jha's (2020) study found that adolescents who played mobile games for an average of two hours daily experienced difficulties in anger management and socialization, ultimately leading to increased hostility and loneliness upon cessation.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive-comparative research design which is a research approach used to analyze and then compare means across different groups without the need to manipulate variables. The questionnaire contains the demographic profile of the teachers, the students' perceived learning styles, the teaching styles that teachers used, and the level of engagement of Gen A students. The primary objective was to identify the impact of learning styles and teachings styles on the learning engagement of Gen A students.

Respondents

The study was conducted in selected schools within Region 10, also known as Northern Mindanao, in the Philippines. Specifically, the study locales include Misamis Oriental, Bukidnon, El Salvador City, and Iligan City. Purposive sampling was used to ensure that respondents meet the specific criteria related to age and educational level to ensure the relevance of the research findings. One hundred Grade 7 and Grade 8 students out of 134, identified as belonging to Generation Alpha, participated in the study. Parental consent was obtained for their participation. Generation Alpha, or Gen A, consists of individuals born starting in 2010, making them the first generation entirely born in the 21st century and following Generation Z. The youngest members of this generation are born in 2024, making the oldest members—those born in 2010—approximately 13 to 14 years old as of 2024 (Debczak, 2024). This age range served as the basis for selecting the participants.

Instrument

The learning styles and teaching styles in this study were measured using a tool developed by Styx (2024), while Gen A students' learning engagement was assessed using a survey questionnaire adapted from Reeve (2013). Before the full study, the research instruments were piloted with 30 Gen A students who were not part of the main sample. To ensure the reliability of the instruments, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was computed, yielding values within the acceptable range of 0.7 to 0.95. These results confirm the strong internal consistency and reliability of the instruments.

Specifically, Cronbach's alpha coefficients of 0.927 for learning styles, 0.913 for teaching styles, and 0.905 for learning engagement fall within the 'excellent' range (George and Mallery, 2018). These high values indicate that the questionnaire items for each variable are consistently measuring what they are intended to measure, enhancing the credibility of the results. The strong internal consistency of the instruments ensures that data collected from them are reliable and consistent over time, a critical factor for meaningful educational research.

In addition, these reliability measures instill confidence in the research findings, as they confirm that the tools are robust enough to capture the Gen A students' learning experiences. This solid foundation of instrument reliability is essential not only for this study but also for future educational assessments and evaluations that may draw from these findings. The use of reliable instruments is key to producing actionable insights, allowing educators to tailor teaching strategies that align more effectively with students' learning preferences and engagement levels.

Procedure

To collect the data, the researchers first obtained permission from the school principals at the study sites. They also secured consent from the parents for their children's participation. Following this, the researchers scheduled appointments with the students to administer the questionnaires. During these sessions, an interview survey was conducted, with each researcher reading the questions aloud and recording the students' responses. This approach enabled the researchers to ensure that the students comprehended the questions and to address any clarifications needed by the participants.

Ethical Considerations

This study rigorously adhered to established research ethics protocols, particularly focusing on obtaining free and prior informed consent from the parents and assent from the students. The confidentiality of the data was a top priority, and the principles outlined in Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, were strictly followed. The researchers thoroughly explained these confidentiality measures to both the parents and participants, ensuring that they understood how their personal information would be protected. This included detailing the specific steps taken to safeguard data, such as anonymizing responses and securely storing all collected information. By emphasizing these ethical standards, the study aimed to foster trust and transparency with all involved parties.

Results and Discussion

Gen A Students' Assessment of their Learning Styles

Visual. Table 1 presents the learning styles of Gen A students in terms of Visual. The overall mean score for Gen A students' assessment of their learning styles is 4.43, indicating a strong agreement across all indicators. This suggests that Gen A students highly endorse visual learning strategies and exhibit consistent behaviors such as doodling, note-taking, and using visual aids like flashcards to enhance their learning experience. This high level of agreement implies the importance of incorporating visual elements into instructional methods to optimize learning outcomes for Gen A students. Educators should consider implementing visual learning strategies to cater to the preferences and needs of these students, ultimately fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

Table 1. *Profile of Gen A's visual learning style*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	I enjoy doodling, and even my notes have lots of pictures and arrows in them	4.80	0.26	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	I find that I remember something better if I write it down.	4.55	0.17	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	I often get lost or have difficulty following directions if I only listen and don't write down the instructions.	4.35	0.22	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	I prefer looking at the person while listening; it helps me stay focused.	4.15	0.33	Strongly Agree	High
5.	I prefer using flashcards to help me retain material for tests.	4.30	0.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Mean		4.43	0.29	Strongly Agree	Very High

Meanwhile, the indicator with the highest mean score is "I enjoy doodling, and even my notes have lots of pictures and arrows in them" with a mean score of 4.80. This exceptionally high score indicates that the majority of Gen A students strongly endorse the use of visual aids and graphical representations in their learning process. Such a preference suggests that educators should integrate more visual elements into their teaching methods, such as incorporating diagrams, illustrations, and mind maps to enhance comprehension and retention. By leveraging students' affinity for visual learning, educators can create more engaging and impactful instructional experiences that cater to their learning preferences and promote a deeper understanding of the material.

However, the indicator with the lowest mean score is "I prefer looking at the person while listening; it helps me stay focused" with a mean score of 4.15. Despite being the lowest mean score among the indicators, it still reflects a strong agreement among Gen A students. However, compared to other indicators, the slightly lower score suggests that while looking at the person while listening is valued, it may not be as preferred or frequently utilized as other visual learning methods. Educators should acknowledge the popularity of maintaining eye contact among students and continue to incorporate it into instructional practices, but also explore alternative visual learning strategies to ensure a well-rounded approach that caters to diverse learning preferences within the Gen A student population.

Auditory. Table 2 shows the learning styles of Gen A students in terms of Auditory, revealing a strong preference for auditory methods of learning with an overall mean score of 4.11. This indicates that students tend to favor techniques involving hearing and listening in their learning process. Specifically, the indicator "I remember things I hear, rather than things I see or read" scored the highest at 4.30, highlighting students' proficiency in retaining auditory information. Given this preference, educators could enhance their teaching methods by incorporating more auditory elements such as lectures and discussions to capitalize on students' strong auditory learning

capabilities.

Table 2. Profile of Gen A's auditory learning style

	Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1.	I notice that my written work doesn't look neat. My papers often have crossed-out words and erasures.	4.05	0.65	Agree	High
2.	I find it tough to comprehend papers with very small print, blotchy dittos, or poor copies.	4.08	0.40	Agree	High
3.	I understand how to do something if someone tells me, rather than having to read the same thing myself.	4.00	0.38	Agree	High
4.	I remember things I hear, rather than things I see or read.	4.30	0.27	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.	I prefer to learn new information through a lecture; I would choose to hear it rather than read it.	4.10	0.25	Agree	High
Overall Mean		4.11	0.39	Agree	High

The lowest mean is 4.00, which corresponds to the statement "I understand how to do something if someone tells me, rather than having to read the same thing myself." This indicator reflects a preference for auditory learning over reading. The lowest mean value, while still high, indicates that among the various learning preferences measured, students slightly less prefer auditory instruction compared to other forms of learning, such as remembering things they hear or learning through lectures. This suggests that while auditory learning is effective, there might be a slightly greater need to reinforce this method with supplementary visual aids or hands-on activities to ensure comprehensive understanding and engagement. Educators should consider integrating multiple teaching approaches to cater to diverse learning preferences and enhance overall student engagement and comprehension.

Kinesthetic. Table 3 presents the learning styles of Gen A students in terms of Kinesthetic. The overall mean score for Gen A students' assessment of their learning styles is 4.24, indicating a strong agreement across all indicators. This suggests that Gen A students highly endorse kinesthetic learning strategies and exhibit consistent behaviors such as preferring hands-on learning experiences and needing physical movement to enhance their learning experience. This high level of agreement implies the importance of incorporating kinesthetic elements into instructional methods to optimize learning outcomes for Gen A students. Educators should consider implementing kinesthetic learning strategies to cater to the preferences and needs of these students, ultimately fostering a more engaging and effective learning environment.

Table 3. Profile of Gen A's kinesthetic learning style

	Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1.	When I study at a desk, it's not comfortable for me.	4.21	0.24	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	I learn best when I'm shown how to do something and when I have the opportunity to do it myself.	4.25	0.38	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	I find it hard to independently study at my desk.	4.27	0.47	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	I tend to solve problems through a more trial-and-error approach, rather than following a step-by-step method.	4.25	0.28	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.	I think better when I have the freedom to move around.	4.22	0.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Mean		4.24	0.36	Strongly Agree	Very High

Meanwhile, the indicator with the highest mean score is "I find it hard to independently study at my desk" with a mean score of 4.27. This exceptionally high score indicates that the majority of Gen A students strongly prefer varied and adaptable study spaces that accommodate their kinesthetic needs. Such a preference suggests that educators should integrate more flexible and interactive study environments into their teaching methods, such as providing opportunities for movement and hands-on activities to enhance comprehension and retention. By leveraging students' affinity for kinesthetic learning, educators can create more engaging and impactful instructional experiences that cater to their learning preferences and promote deeper understanding of the material.

However, the indicator with the lowest mean score is "When I study at a desk, it's not comfortable for me" with a mean score of 4.21. Despite being the lowest mean score among the indicators, it still reflects a strong agreement among Gen A students. However, compared to other indicators, the slightly lower score suggests that while alternative study environments are valued, they may not be as preferred or frequently utilized as other kinesthetic learning methods. Educators should acknowledge the importance of comfort in study environments and continue to explore alternative settings, but also ensure a well-rounded approach that caters to diverse learning preferences within the Gen A student population.

Gen A Students' Assessment of Teachers' Teaching Styles

Authoritative or Lecture Style. Table 4 illustrates how students assess their teachers' teaching styles, specifically focusing on the Authoritative or Lecture Style. The overall mean score for students' assessment of this teaching style is 3.38, indicating a moderately high level of agreement among students. This suggests that while there is a general agreement with the use of authoritative or lecture-style teaching methods, there may also be some variation in students' perceptions of specific aspects of this teaching style.

The indicator with the highest mean score is "My teacher uses plain lectures or class discussions" with a mean score of 3.70. This

indicates a high level of agreement among students that their teachers primarily use lectures or class discussions as a teaching method. It suggests that students perceive this as a predominant approach in their learning experience.

Table 4. *Gen A students' assessment of teachers' teaching style (authoritative or lecture style)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	My teacher uses plain lectures or class discussions.	3.70	0.54	Agree	High
2.	My teacher conducts extra sessions so that we can acquire more information.	3.55	0.81	Agree	High
3.	My teacher distributes a copy of the lesson to us.	3.15	0.43	Slightly Agree	Moderately High
4.	My teacher uses lectures as the main teaching style for the entire subject.	3.35	0.18	Slightly Agree	Moderately High
5.	My teacher encourages learning through listening to their lecture.	3.35	0.24	Slightly Agree	Moderately High
6.	My teacher provides lessons and activities that focus on competency-based learning.	3.30	0.31	Slightly Agree	Moderately High
7.	My teacher supports teacher-centered learning.	3.25	0.25	Slightly Agree	Moderately High
	Overall Mean	3.38	0.39	Slightly Agree	Moderately High

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score is "My teacher distributes a copy of the lesson to us" with a mean score of 3.15. While still indicating a moderately high level of agreement, this score suggests that students may perceive some limitations or opportunities for improvement in terms of material distribution within the teaching style. It implies that while the teaching approach may predominantly be authoritative or lecture-based, there is room for further enhancement of resource distribution to support student learning. Delegator or Group Style. Table 5 provides an assessment of the teachers' teaching styles in terms of the Delegator or Group Style, based on various indicators. The overall mean score for the Delegator or Group Style teaching is 4.40, indicating a very high level of agreement among students. Consequently, there is a strong consensus among students regarding their teachers' utilization of delegator or group-style teaching methods, characterized by active learning, collaboration, and problem-solving within the classroom setting.

Among the indicators, "My teacher groups us and gives us a certain topic to discuss and defend" received the highest mean score of 4.46. This signifies a robust agreement among students regarding the teacher's facilitation of group discussions and collaborative activities, fostering critical thinking and communication skills. Furthermore, it reflects positively on the teacher's ability to promote active engagement and interaction among students within the delegator or group-style framework.

Table 5. *Gen A students' assessment of teachers' teaching style (delegator or group style)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	My teacher uses lab activities to encourage active learning, interaction, participation, and collaboration among students.	4.32	0.32	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	My teacher observes us while we perform tasks.	4.43	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	My teacher sees themselves as a delegator.	4.30	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	My teacher consults the results of certain activities that they assign.	4.45	0.58	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.	My teacher groups us and gives us a certain topic to discuss and defend.	4.46	0.38	Strongly Agree	Very High
6.	My teacher tries their best to solve our problems.	4.44	0.52	Strongly Agree	Very High
7.	My teacher uses debate as a strategy to make us think and articulate our ideas.	4.40	0.37	Strongly Agree	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.40	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High

Conversely, the indicator with the lowest mean score is "My teacher sees themselves as a delegator" with a mean score of 4.30. Although still indicative of a strong agreement, this score suggests a slightly lower level of consensus among students regarding the teacher's self-perception as a delegator. Consequently, it may imply some variability in students' perceptions of the teacher's role in facilitating group dynamics and delegating tasks within the classroom context.

Demonstrator or Coach Style. Table 6 presents students' assessment of the teachers' teaching styles in terms of the Demonstrator or Coach Style. The overall mean score of 4.25 indicates a very high level of consensus among students regarding the effectiveness of their teachers in employing demonstrator or coach-style teaching methods. Consequently, students highly appreciate, and value instructional approaches characterized by demonstration, multimedia utilization, and guidance from the teacher.

Transitioning to the highest mean indicator, "My teacher allows us to observe carefully what they present" received the highest mean score of 4.31. This underlies the importance students place on the teacher's ability to facilitate clear and comprehensive learning experiences through effective demonstration and presentation. Additionally, it reflects positively on the teacher's role in promoting active observation and engagement among students, contributing to a highly conducive learning environment.

Conversely, all indicators received high mean scores, with no clear outlier indicating a lowest mean score. Therefore, while all aspects of the Demonstrator or Coach Style teaching received strong agreement from students, there are no specific areas where students perceive less effectiveness or satisfaction. This suggests a consistent and comprehensive implementation of demonstrator or coach-

style teaching methods by the teachers, contributing to positive learning outcomes across various dimensions.

Table 6. *Gen A students' assessment of teachers' teaching style (demonstrator or coach style)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	My teacher is the one who demonstrates the class activity.	4.21	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	My teacher uses multimedia presentations for us.	4.27	0.72	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	My teacher utilizes their expertise in teaching.	4.18	0.74	Agree	High
4.	My teacher employs a variety of forms including lectures, multimedia, presentations, and demonstrations.	4.20	0.83	Agree	High
5.	My teacher allows us to observe carefully what they present.	4.31	0.29	Strongly Agree	Very High
6.	My teacher is there to guide us in our daily tasks.	4.26	0.34	Strongly Agree	Very High
7.	My teacher uses demonstration as a teaching style for the entire subject they handle.	4.23	0.37	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Mean		4.25	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High

Conversely, all indicators received high mean scores, with no clear outlier indicating a lowest mean score. Therefore, while all aspects of the Demonstrator or Coach Style teaching received strong agreement from students, there are no specific areas where students perceive less effectiveness or satisfaction. This suggests a consistent and comprehensive implementation of demonstrator or coach-style teaching methods by the teachers, contributing to positive learning outcomes across various dimensions.

Facilitator or Activity Style. Table 7 illustrates how students assess their teachers' teaching styles in terms of the Facilitator or Activity Style. The overall mean score for students' assessment of this teaching style is 4.78, indicating a very high level of agreement among students. This suggests that students highly appreciate instructional approaches characterized by facilitation, active participation, and the encouragement of independent learning.

The indicator with the highest mean score is "My teacher facilitates and monitors appropriate interaction among us students" with a mean score of 4.83. This emphasizes the paramount importance students attach to the teacher's role in fostering a supportive and interactive learning environment. Furthermore, it underscores the teacher's capacity to promote meaningful interactions among students, thereby enhancing collaboration, critical thinking, and social-emotional development.

Table 7. *Gen A students' assessment of teachers' teaching style (facilitator or activity style)*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	In my class, my teacher acts as a facilitator.	4.78	0.42	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	My teacher lets us ask questions regarding our topic.	4.82	0.45	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	My teacher consults us to correct problems and ensure we clearly understand, keeping us on track.	4.80	0.36	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	My teacher encourages us to participate in activities to develop our special abilities.	4.70	0.35	Strongly Agree	Very High
5.	My teacher uses facilitating as the sole teaching style for the entire subject.	4.75	0.46	Strongly Agree	Very High
6.	My teacher encourages independent creativity from us.	4.80	0.49	Strongly Agree	Very High
7.	My teacher facilitates and monitors appropriate interaction among us students.	4.83	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Mean		4.78	0.45	Strongly Agree	Very High

Conversely, since all indicators received high mean scores, there isn't a discernible lowest mean score. This suggests a consistent and comprehensive integration of facilitator or activity-style teaching methods by the teachers. Students perceive their teachers as consistently facilitating active learning and engagement across various dimensions, with no specific areas where students perceive less effectiveness or satisfaction.

Gen A Students' Level of Engagement

Behavioral Engagement. Table 8 presents the level of behavioral engagement of Gen A students. The overall mean score of 4.44 indicates a very high level of Behavioral Engagement among Gen A students. This suggests a strong consensus among students regarding their active participation and involvement in class activities, fostering a conducive learning environment.

The indicator with the highest mean score is "When I am in my class, I listen very carefully," with a mean score of 4.70. This signifies a very high level of agreement among students, emphasizing their attentive behavior during class sessions and their dedication to understanding the instructional content.

Conversely, "I try to do well in our class" received the lowest mean score of 4.15. Although still indicative of agreement, this score suggests a slightly lower level of motivation or self-perceived performance among students. Addressing this aspect could further enhance students' engagement and overall learning experiences.

Overall, the high level of Behavioral Engagement among Gen A students underscores their active involvement in class activities. Educators may explore strategies to bolster students' motivation and confidence, ultimately optimizing their learning outcomes.

Table 8. *Level of behavioral engagement of Gen A students*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	When I am in my class, I listen very carefully.	4.70	0.62	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	I try to do well in our class.	4.50	0.72	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	I pay attention in our class.	4.40	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	I work as hard as I can in our class.	4.15	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall Mean		4.44	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very High

Agentic Engagement. Table 9 presents the level of agentic engagement among Gen A students. The overall mean score of 4.24 indicates a very high level of agreement among students regarding their proactive engagement in the learning process. This suggests that students are actively involved in shaping their learning experiences, contributing to a positive and dynamic classroom environment.

The indicator with the highest mean score is "I let my teacher know what I need and want" with a mean score of 4.44. This indicates a very high level of agreement among students, emphasizing their proactive approach to seeking clarification and assistance when needed. It demonstrates students' initiative and assertiveness in taking control of their learning journey.

Table 9. *Level of agentic engagement of Gen A students*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	I let my teacher know what I need and want.	4.44	0.34	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	I ask questions to get help.	4.25	0.46	Strongly Agree	Very High
3.	I adjust to the topic so I can learn as much as possible.	4.10	0.65	Agree	High
4.	I try to make our lesson as interesting to me as possible.	4.15	0.82	Agree	High
Overall Mean		4.24	0.57	Strongly Agree	Very High

Conversely, "I adjust to the topic so I can learn as much as possible" recorded the lowest mean score of 4.10. While still indicative of agreement, this score suggests a slightly lower level of proactivity compared to other indicators. It implies that while students are generally adaptive to the topic, they may not always be as proactive in ensuring they learn as much as possible from it. Overall, Gen A students exhibit a high level of Agentic Engagement, actively taking charge of their learning process by seeking assistance, letting their needs and wants be known, and striving to make lessons interesting to themselves.

Cognitive Engagement. Table 10 presents the level of Cognitive Engagement among Gen A students. The overall mean score of 4.04 indicates a high level of agreement among students regarding their cognitive involvement in the learning process. This suggests that students actively apply various cognitive strategies to enhance their understanding and retention of the lesson content.

Meanwhile, "I try to relate our lesson to my prior knowledge" received the highest mean score of 4.25. This indicates a very high level of agreement among students, highlighting their proactive effort to connect new learning with their existing knowledge base. It demonstrates students' ability to integrate new information into their existing mental frameworks, facilitating deeper understanding and retention.

The lowest mean in the provided data is 3.92, which corresponds to the statement "I try to make all the different ideas fit together and make sense when I study our lesson." The lowest mean value, although still high, suggests that students find it slightly more challenging to integrate various ideas and make sense of them compared to other reflective learning strategies. This indicates that while students generally engage in reflective thinking and integration of ideas, they may benefit from additional support in developing these skills. Educators could enhance this aspect of learning by providing structured frameworks, mind maps, and guided discussions that help students see connections between different concepts. By doing so, educators can foster deeper understanding and better integration of new knowledge with existing knowledge, thereby improving overall learning outcomes.

Table 10. *Level of cognitive engagement of Gen A students*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	I try to connect our topic to my personal experiences.	3.94	0.63	Agree	High
2.	I try to make all the different ideas fit together and make sense when I study our lesson.	3.92	0.29	Agree	High
3.	I try to relate our lesson to my prior knowledge.	4.25	0.34	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	I make my own examples to help me understand the concept of our lesson.	4.05	0.37	Agree	High
Overall Mean		4.04	0.41	Agree	High

Emotional Engagement. Table 11 depicts the Emotional Engagement levels of Gen A students, with an overall mean score of 4.21, indicating a strong agreement among students regarding their emotional experiences in the classroom. This suggests that students generally perceive their learning environment positively, experiencing excitement, enjoyment, and a sense of involvement during class activities.

The indicator with the highest mean score is "I feel excited about every task" with a mean score of 4.75. This underscores a very high level of agreement among students regarding their enthusiasm towards academic tasks, signifying a positive emotional disposition

towards learning. Such excitement can foster motivation and active participation in classroom activities.

Table 11. *Level of emotional engagement of Gen A students*

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1.	I feel excited about every task.	4.75	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High
2.	I find fun in our lessons.	3.69	0.70	Agree	High
3.	I enjoy learning things in our class.	4.32	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very High
4.	I feel good in our class.	3.85	0.65	Agree	High
5.	I get myself involved in our class	4.42	0.56	Strongly Agree	Very High
	Overall Mean	4.21	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very High

Conversely, "I find fun in our lessons" and "I feel good in our class" both received slightly lower mean scores of 3.69 and 3.85 respectively. While still indicative of agreement, these scores suggest a marginally reduced emphasis on the enjoyment and overall emotional well-being within the classroom. It implies an opportunity to further enhance students' positive emotional experiences during learning activities.

In summary, Gen A students demonstrate a high level of Emotional Engagement, expressing excitement, enjoyment, and a sense of involvement in classroom tasks. Educators can capitalize on students' enthusiasm to create a supportive and engaging learning environment, fostering continuous motivation and positive emotional experiences.

Gen A Students' Learning Engagement and Learning Styles

Table 12 presents the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results for student engagement when grouped according to learning styles. The ANOVA indicates a significant difference on learning engagement when grouped according to learning styles. The sum of squares between groups (35.078) reflects the variability in student engagement that can be attributed to differences in learning styles, while the sum of squares within groups (19.533) represents the variability within each learning style group. The total sum of squares (54.611) combines the overall variability in student engagement across all groups and individuals.

The F-statistic (87.099) is the ratio of the mean square between groups to the mean square within groups, illustrating the extent to which learning styles explain the variability in engagement compared to random variability within groups. The significance value (p-value) of .000 indicates a very low probability that the observed differences in engagement are due to chance. Since this p-value is well below the conventional threshold of 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis, concluding that there is a statistically significant difference in student engagement among the different learning style groups. The substantial F-value and minimal p-value strongly suggest that learning styles significantly impact student engagement.

Table 12. *Analysis of Variance of student engagement when grouped according to students' learning styles*

<i>Student Engagement</i>	<i>ANOVA</i>				
	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Between Groups	35.078	2	17.539	87.099	.000
Within Groups	19.533	97	.201		
Total	54.611	99			

A range of studies have explored the relationship between learning styles and student engagement. Nicholson (2019) and Halif et al. (2020) both found that visual learning style was associated with higher engagement, with Halif also noting the moderating effects of student motivation. Haider et al. (2023) further emphasized the role of teacher teaching approaches, with an autonomous-supportive style correlating with higher engagement. Naiker et al. (2022) highlighted the impact of age on engagement, with younger students showing lower levels. These findings suggest that a combination of individual learning styles, motivation, teaching approaches, and age can significantly influence student engagement.

The significant impact of learning styles on student engagement suggests that educators should tailor their instructional methods to accommodate diverse learning preferences, incorporating a variety of teaching techniques such as visual, auditory, and kinesthetic methods to enhance engagement and learning outcomes. This evidence supports the development of personalized learning plans and underscores the importance of teacher training in diverse instructional strategies. For policymakers, these findings highlight the need for educational frameworks that recognize and accommodate diverse learning styles, promoting flexible curricula and differentiated instruction to improve student engagement and educational success.

Table 13 presents the Scheffe post-hoc test results for students' engagement when grouped according to learning styles. The multiple comparisons reveal significant differences in engagement between all pairs of learning styles. Visual learners exhibit significantly higher engagement than both kinesthetic learners (mean difference = 0.76357, $p = .000$) and auditory learners (mean difference = 1.46466, $p = .000$).

Similarly, kinesthetic learners show significantly higher engagement than auditory learners (mean difference = 0.70109, $p = .000$). The

95% confidence intervals for these differences do not include zero, further confirming the significance of these findings. These results indicate that visual learners are the most engaged, followed by kinesthetic learners, with auditory learners being the least engaged among the groups.

Table 13. *Scheffe post-hoc test results*

Students' Engagement		Multiple Comparisons				
(I) LearningStyles	(J) LearningStyles	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Visual Learners	Kinesthetic Learners	.76357*	.10554	.000	.5012	1.0259
	Auditory Learners	1.46466*	.11380	.000	1.1818	1.7476
Kinesthetic Learners	Visual Learners	-.76357*	.10554	.000	-1.0259	-.5012
	Auditory Learners	.70109*	.12529	.000	.3896	1.0126
Auditory Learners	Visual Learners	-1.46466*	.11380	.000	-1.7476	-1.1818
	Kinesthetic Learners	-.70109*	.12529	.000	-1.0126	-.3896

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Research on the variance of students' engagement when grouped according to learning styles has yielded interesting findings. Halif et al. (2020) found that visual learners tend to have higher classroom engagement compared to auditory and kinesthetic learners, with motivation playing a moderating role. This is supported by Ariastuti and Wahyudin (2022), who reported a significant effect of learning style on academic performance, with visual learners performing better. However, Çakıroğlu et al. (2019) found that auditory learners perceive higher cognitive load in multimedia learning, which could potentially impact their engagement. Lastly, Dipasupil et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of understanding students' engagement strategies, which could be influenced by their learning styles. These studies collectively suggest that while visual learners may have higher engagement, the relationship between learning styles and engagement is complex and multifaceted.

The significant differences in student engagement among visual, kinesthetic, and auditory learners imply the necessity for educators to consider these varying levels of engagement when designing and implementing instructional strategies. By integrating more visual and kinesthetic elements into their teaching methods, educators can enhance overall student engagement, especially for auditory learners who were found to be the least engaged.

These findings suggest the need for a balanced approach that caters to all learning styles, potentially through multimodal instructional strategies that incorporate visual aids, hands-on activities, and auditory components to create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment. Additionally, teacher training programs should emphasize the importance of recognizing and addressing diverse learning styles to optimize student engagement and learning outcomes.

Difference in Gen A Students' Learning Engagement when Grouped According to Teaching Styles

Table 14 presents the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) results for student engagement when grouped according to teachers' teaching styles. The ANOVA results reveal a significant effect of teaching styles on student engagement. The sum of squares between groups (34.464) indicates the variability in student engagement attributable to differences in teaching styles, while the sum of squares within groups (17.851) represents the variability within each teaching style group. The total sum of squares (52.316) combines the overall variability in student engagement across all groups and individuals.

Table 14. *Analysis of Variance of student engagement when grouped according to the teachers' teaching styles*

ANOVA					
Students' Engagement	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	34.464	3	11.488	61.780	.000
Within Groups	17.851	96	.186		
Total	52.316	99			

The F-statistic (61.780) is the ratio of the mean square between groups to the mean square within groups, demonstrating the extent to which teaching styles explain the variability in engagement compared to random variability within groups. The significance value (p-value) of .000 indicates a very low probability that the observed differences in engagement are due to chance. Given this p-value is well below the conventional threshold of 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis, concluding that there is a statistically significant difference in student engagement among the different teaching style groups. The high F-value and low p-value strongly suggest that teaching styles significantly impact student engagement.

Research consistently shows that teachers' instructional techniques significantly impact student engagement (Afzal, 2022). This underscores the need for educators to vary their teaching styles to cater to different learning preferences (Harris, 2020). Innovative and interactive instructional strategies, such as technology-based activities and group reports, have been found to enhance student participation in the classroom (Dhamija & Dhamija 2020; Abulhul, 2021). These findings highlight the importance of incorporating a

mix of instructional strategies, including interactive activities, discussions, visual aids, and hands-on learning, to appeal to a broader range of students.

School administrators should support professional development programs that train teachers in diverse instructional techniques, helping them to understand and implement teaching styles that maximize student engagement. Research consistently underscores the importance of professional development programs for teachers, particularly in diverse instructional techniques and teaching styles that maximize student engagement (Courtney, 2023; Kilag & Sasan, 2023; Singh, 2023; Makuachukwu, 2023). These programs can equip teachers with the skills to create more dynamic and responsive learning environments. For policymakers, these findings underscore the need to develop educational policies that promote flexibility in teaching approaches and support continuous teacher training. By recognizing the impact of teaching styles on student engagement, educational frameworks can be designed to encourage innovative teaching practices that adapt to the needs of all students, ultimately leading to improved academic outcomes and a more engaging learning experience.

The findings indicate a clear association (p -value .000) between the instructional methods employed by teachers and students' levels of engagement in the learning process. Consistent with previous research (Davis & Smith, 2019), authoritarian teaching styles were found to be associated with lower levels of student engagement, potentially due to the restrictive nature of such approaches. In contrast, student-centered teaching styles, such as facilitator or activity styles, were associated with higher levels of engagement, echoing the principles of learner-centered pedagogy (Rubie-Davies, 2015). These findings highlight the importance of adopting facilitative and delegative approaches that empower students to take ownership of their learning experiences and foster active participation. By aligning teaching practices with the diverse needs and preferences of Generation Alpha students, educators can create inclusive and dynamic learning environments conducive to meaningful learning experiences and positive academic outcomes.

Table 15 presents the Scheffe post-hoc test results for students' engagement when grouped according to teachers' teaching styles. The multiple comparisons reveal significant differences in engagement among the various teaching styles.

Authoritative teaching style results in significantly lower student engagement compared to Delegator (-1.27041, $p = .000$), Demonstrator (-.66046, $p = .000$), and Facilitator (-1.59166, $p = .000$). Delegator teaching style shows significantly higher engagement compared to Authoritative (1.27041, $p = .000$) and Demonstrator (.60995, $p = .000$) but not significantly different from Facilitator (-.32125, $p = .052$). Demonstrator teaching style results in significantly higher engagement than Authoritative (.66046, $p = .000$) and significantly lower engagement than Delegator (-.60995, $p = .000$) and Facilitator (-.93121, $p = .000$). Lastly, the Facilitator teaching style leads to significantly higher engagement compared to Authoritative (1.59166, $p = .000$) and Demonstrator (.93121, $p = .000$) but not significantly different from Delegator (.32125, $p = .052$). These differences indicate that the Facilitator and Delegator teaching styles tend to result in higher student engagement compared to Authoritative and Demonstrator styles.

Table 15. *Scheffe post-hoc test*

<i>Students' Engagement</i>		<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>					
		<i>(I) Teaching Styles</i>	<i>(J) Teaching Styles</i>	<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>
						<i>Lower Bound</i>	<i>Upper Bound</i>
Authoritative	Delegator		-1.27041*	.12913	.000	-1.6379	-.9029
	Demonstrator		-.66046*	.13369	.000	-1.0409	-.2800
	Facilitator		-1.59166*	.12564	.000	-1.9492	-1.2341
Delegator	Authoritative		1.27041*	.12913	.000	.9029	1.6379
	Demonstrator		.60995*	.12236	.000	.2617	.9582
	Facilitator		-.32125	.11351	.052	-.6443	.0018
Demonstrator	Authoritative		.66046*	.13369	.000	.2800	1.0409
	Delegator		-.60995*	.12236	.000	-.9582	-.2617
	Facilitator		-.93121*	.11867	.000	-1.2689	-.5935
Facilitator	Authoritative		1.59166*	.12564	.000	1.2341	1.9492
	Delegator		.32125	.11351	.052	-.0018	.6443
	Demonstrator		.93121*	.11867	.000	.5935	1.2689

*The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Research on the variance of students' engagement when grouped according to teachers' teaching styles reveals significant differences. Leo et al. (2022) found that students' engagement varied based on their perceptions of teachers' need-supportive and need-thwarting behaviors. Inayat and Ali (2020) further explored this, identifying a correlation between perceived autonomy support teaching style and students' engagement, curiosity, and exploration. Fernández-García et al. (2021) highlighted the influence of teacher effectiveness, particularly in the domains of classroom management, activating teaching, and differentiation, on students' academic engagement. Lastly, Ruqaishi (2022) emphasized the role of emotional engagement in teachers' overall engagement, with a focus on the impact of students' learning environment. These studies collectively underscore the significant impact of teachers' teaching styles on students' engagement, with a particular emphasis on the need for autonomy support, effective classroom management, and emotional engagement.

The significant differences in student engagement based on teachers' teaching styles have important implications for educational

practices and policies. The findings suggest that teaching styles such as Facilitator and Delegator, which are associated with higher student engagement, should be encouraged and integrated into teaching strategies. This could involve providing teachers with professional development opportunities to learn and implement these styles effectively. Additionally, educational institutions should consider these results when designing curricula and instructional approaches to maximize student engagement and academic outcomes. Policymakers should support initiatives that promote flexible and adaptive teaching methods, ensuring that teachers are equipped to engage students effectively.

Overall, recognizing the impact of different teaching styles on student engagement can lead to more dynamic and responsive educational environments that cater to the diverse needs of students.

Conclusions

The analysis of student engagement based on learning styles reveals significant differences among visual, kinesthetic, and auditory learners. Visual learners exhibit the highest engagement levels, followed by kinesthetic learners, with auditory learners showing the least engagement. This suggests that educators should consider these disparities when planning instructional strategies, aiming for a balanced approach that accommodates various learning styles. Incorporating visual and kinesthetic elements into teaching methods can enhance overall engagement, particularly for auditory learners who may struggle with traditional approaches. Additionally, teacher training programs should prioritize understanding and addressing diverse learning styles to optimize student engagement and learning outcomes.

Moreover, when classified according to teaching styles, Gen A students exhibit significant differences in their learning engagement. This indicates that teaching styles are a key factor influencing the variation in student engagement. Specifically, authoritative teaching styles tend to result in lower levels of student engagement compared to more facilitative or delegative approaches, which foster higher engagement levels.

These findings carry crucial implications for educational practices and policies. Encouraging the adoption of student-centered teaching styles, such as facilitator or delegator approaches, can enhance student engagement and improve overall academic outcomes. This necessitates providing professional development opportunities for teachers to learn and implement these styles effectively. Thus, recognizing the influence of teaching styles on student engagement can lead to more dynamic and inclusive learning environments. By supporting initiatives that promote flexible teaching methods and continuous teacher training, policymakers can contribute to creating educational frameworks that optimize student engagement and foster meaningful learning experiences.

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